

FINE NEEDLE ASPIRATION CYTOLOGY IN THE DIAGNOSIS OF LYMPH NODE MALIGNANCIES -A SIMPLE AND SENSITIVE TOOL

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Abstract :

Introduction:

Enlarged lymph nodes are readily accessible for fine needle aspiration and hence fine needle aspiration cytology is very simple and important diagnostic tool for lymph node lesions. This study was undertaken with the aim of highlighting the role of FNAC's of lymph nodes in the diagnosis of suspected and unsuspected malignancies in lymph node. Malignancies in lymph nodes in our country are predominantly metastatic in nature ranging from 65.7% and 80.4% and lymphomas ranging from 2% to 15.3% amongst lymph nodes aspirated from all sites.

Materials and method: This is a cross sectional hospital based study on 30 patients diagnosed to have primary or secondary lymph node malignancy by cytology and confirmed by histopathology between January 2023- June 2023 at a tertiary care center. Inadequate smear were excluded from the study. Detailed history, clinical examination and relevant investigations were documented. The correlation between cytopathological diagnosis and histopathological diagnosis of lymph nodes was done.

Observations and Results: 25 cases of metastatic malignancy and 2 cases of lymphomas were diagnosed by FNAC of lymph nodes and histopathological correlation was available in all cases. 3 cases were suspected on FNAC which did not correlate with histopathological findings.

Summary/ Conclusion:

FNAC of lymph nodes is very useful, sensitive and reliable diagnostic tool in the diagnosis of lymph node malignancies.

Key Words: Fine needle aspiration cytology, lymph node, malignancy.

INTRODUCTION

Lymphadenopathy is one of the most common clinical presentations of patients attending outdoor clinics in most hospitals.

The etiology varies from an infective to neoplastic condition.¹

FNAC has become a simplified tool in early diagnosis as it causes minimal trauma and less complications.²

FNAC is more economical as compared to more expensive surgical excision biopsies in developing countries.³

The incidence of lymphoid malignancies in our country varies from 65.7% to 80.4% for metastatic and from 2% to 15.3% for lymphomas.^{6,7,8}

Aims and Objectives

To study the utility of FNAC in lymphoid malignancy along with its histopathological correlation.

Materials and method: Study duration 6 months [January 2023 to June 2023].

Inclusion criteria :

(1)All the cases suspected of malignancies on FNAC along with histopathological follow-up.

(2) Adequately cellular smears.

(3)All age groups were included.

Exclusion criteria:

Inadequate smears were excluded from the study.

Sample size: 30 cases with histopathological correlation were taken in this study.

All relevant history, clinical examination findings were recorded from requisition forms.

The FNAC of lymph node was done with subsequent preparation of air dried and fixed smear.

Air dried smears were stained with Hematoxylin-Eosin and Leishman stain.

Fixed smears were stained with Papanicolaou stain.

Observations and Results :

Out of 30 cases studied on FNAC , 25[83.33%] were diagnosed as metastatic malignancy and 2[6.66%] cases pointed towards lymphoma. Histopathological correlations were established in 27 of these cases. The remaining 3 cases exhibited a lack of histopathological correlation.

The age group varied from 22 to 82 years, with males (16 cases, 59%) being more involved than females (11 cases, 41%).

Gender distribution

AGE DISTRIBUTION

Table No. 1: Lymph node aspirate cytological diagnosis

Metastatic	cervical	Axillary	Inguinal	supraclavicular	Total
Squamous cell carcinoma	12		1		13
Ductal carcinoma breast		7			7
Adenocarcinoma				1	1
Epithelial malignancy	1				1
Thyroid carcinoma	2				2
Melanoma primary	1				1
Hodgkin	1				1
Non-Hodgkin	1				1
Total	18	7	1	1	27

Photomicrograph showing Atypical cells with mixed lymphoid population.

Leishman stain X 400.

Figure no -1

Figure no -1

Histopathology

Photomicrograph showing classical RS cells and lacunar cells.

H & E stain X 400.

Figure no-2

Figure no-2

Photomicrograph of a smear of melanoma, showing a pleomorphic population of tumour cells. Pigment-laden cells also seen.

Leishman stain x 400.

Figure no -3

Figure no -3

Cytology smear:-Metastasis of follicular carcinoma of the thyroid

Photomicrograph showing tumour cells resembling thyroid follicular cells arranged in follicles as well as singly scattered.

Leishman stain x400

Figure no-4.

Figure no-4.

In 30 cases under study, 25 were diagnosed with metastatic lymph node malignancy. These findings were validated through histopathological examination.

In cytology smear, 2 out of 30 cases were identified as lymphoproliferative disorder. Subsequent histopathological analysis confirmed these cases as Hodgkin's and non-Hodgkin's lymphoma.

3 out of 30 cases were flagged as suspicious for lymphoproliferative disorder. Histopathological analysis revealed all three to be cases of reactive hyperplasia.

Table no.2 Distribution of cases according to tumour site.

Lymph node metastatic site	No. Cases	Percentage	Tumour site
Cervical	18	66.66%	Tongue-3 Oral cavity-8 Pyriiform sinus-1 Oesophagus-1 Thyroid-2 Lymphoma-2 Plantar aspect of foot -1
Axillary	7	25.92%	Breast-7
Inguinal	1	3.70%	Penis-1
Supraclavicular	1	3.70%	Stomach -1
Total	27	100%	

Table no.3 CYTOHISTOPATHOLOGICAL CORRELATION

Lymph node site	No of Cases	Cytology Diagnosis	Histopathology Diagnosis	Total
Cervical	18			
		Metastasis of SCC-12	Metastasis of SCC-12	12
		Metastasis of Follicular Carcinoma Thyroid - 1	Metastasis of Follicular Carcinoma Thyroid - 1	1
		Metastasis of Papillary Carcinoma Thyroid - 1	Metastasis of Papillary Carcinoma Thyroid - 1	1
		Lymphoma – 2	Lymphoma - 2	2
		Melanoma – 1	Melanoma – 1	1
		Epithelial carcinoma - 1	Epithelial carcinoma - 1	1
Axillary	7	Metastasis of IDC -7	Metastasis of IDC -7	7
Inguinal	1	Metastasis of SCC-1	Metastasis of SCC-1	1
Supraclavicular	1	Metastasis of Adenocarcinoma – 1	Metastasis of Adenocarcinoma – 1	1
Total				27

Discussion

Not only direct but guided FNAC can also be accessible for small and deep-seated lymph nodes, which are crucial for diagnosing primary or secondary cancers.⁶⁻⁸

FNAC can also diagnose occult primaries, e.g., Carcinoma of the thyroid, carcinoma of the stomach, carcinoma of the gallbladder, by aspiration of the lymph node.

The primary is frequently present in the oral cavity, and the most common histological type is squamous cell carcinoma.^{6,7}

Table no.4 COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS

	Present Study	Other study
Lymphomas involvement	6.66%	Arora B, Beena KR, et-al-32%
Metastatic lymph node involvement	83.33%	Arora B, Beena KR, et-al-68%
Most common histology type	Squamous cell carcinoma	Steffen Höft et al- Squamous cell carcinoma
Most common lymph node involved	Cervical group of lymph node	Hoft S, Muhle C, Brenner W,etal-Cervical group of lymph node

3 cases were over diagnosed by cytology as lymphoproliferative disorder and turned out to be reactive lymph node hyperplasia on histopathology.

If the aspiration of the reactive node is derived from the large germinal center, the proportion of the large cells (centroblasts and dendritic cells) and the number of mitoses might be impressive enough to suggest malignant lymphoma.

However, Hehn et al., in their series, have quoted that the full range of lymphocyte transformation was still present in a greater proportion of such germinal center aspiration.¹²

According to Landgren et al., the presence of lymphoid cell hyperplasia and subsequent cell division may result in an increase in the number of immature lymphoid cells in reactive lymphoid hyperplasia. Their findings suggest lymphoma should be identified when these immature cells comprise more than 50% of the total cell population.¹³

Conclusion

FNAC of lymph nodes proves to be a very helpful and simple tool for the diagnosis of lymph node malignancy.

It can provide a preliminary diagnosis of lymphomas, which can be confirmed by histopathology and immunohistochemistry. As a result, the cytopathologist is crucial in diagnosing lymph node malignancies

in patients who have not yet been diagnosed with malignancy in the context of clinical, radiological, and laboratory findings.

If any of these findings are suspicious, additional investigation should be performed to overcome the drawbacks and pitfalls of using the cytomorphological features alone.

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